

ACCURATE REMOTE MEASUREMENT OF ROBOT TRAJECTORY MOTION

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ABSTRACT

The development, calibration and evaluation of a two camera opto-electronics remote measuring system is described. The measuring system, developed by the National Bureau of Standards (NBS), precisely tracks in three dimensions the location of infrared emitting LEDs. An approach being developed by NBS will use the system for accurately measuring robot trajectory motion and position within a calibrated work volume. This paper evaluates the performance of the measurement system apart from any specific applications. The measuring system, which uses two tetra-lateral photodiode cameras, has a resolution of approximately 0.01 percent and an absolute accuracy of 0.05 percent along each of the three dimensions of a work volume when using data points from within the center 80 percent of the detector field of view. Accuracy degrades to 0.1 percent when including data points from outside the center 90 percent of the field of view. Data collection rate is 3.3 kHz for one data point (LED) location measurement. Implementation and analysis procedures are also discussed.

INTRODUCTION

A knowledge of the absolute position and orientation of a robot's end effector is essential for accurate control and implementation of the robot in an automated manufacturing environment. Even though many robots achieve an acceptable level of repeatability, their ability to be accurately positioned through off-line program control to any given point and orientation within its work volume is generally lacking. The problem becomes more critical in dynamic applications where additional errors are produced by structural deformations of the robot and sub-optimal closed loop control systems. As robots increase in size and dexterity, the positioning and trajectory errors increase with the size and number of intervening links necessary to allow the end-effector adequate range and degrees of freedom. For these reasons, independent measurements of the three-dimensional (3D) coordinates of arbitrary points on the robot are very desirable. The method should ideally be on-line, noncontacting, have a high resolution, accuracy, and frequency response, and be capable of operating in an industrial environment.

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A number of techniques have been utilized to measure the static 3D accuracy of robots. These methods include the sending of the robot to points which have been previously defined by other high accuracy measurement methods (1,2). Laser tracking (3,4), ball bar measurements (5) and various forms of stereo-triangulation techniques can be used for performing such measurements.

Stereo-triangulation methods involve the direction measurements of target points from accurately known positions in a reference coordinate frame. The measurements are generally made by devices capable of measuring angles in two planes, such as cameras or theodolites. Measurements from two "cameras" are required to determine the 3D location of a single target point, but data from additional cameras may be used to provide redundancy and improve accuracy. Photogrammetric and surveying techniques are well developed and highly accurate, but suffer from being off-line, very slow, and highly labor intensive. Recent advances in optoelectronics have made available a number of devices for making the required angle measurements on-line and at relatively high speeds. Several video based systems capable of digitizing image coordinates of reflective targets have been described for human movement studies (6,7,8). These systems operate at the relatively slow measurement rate of 50 or 60 frames per second, have limited resolution, and do not allow for the identification of targets if more than one is used. Charge-coupled device (CCD) imaging systems have similar drawbacks. The slow measurement rates and low resolution of standard equipment, as well as difficulties associated with extracting information from the images, make such systems of limited value in high accuracy applications.

Large area photodiodes using light emitting diodes (LEDs), as active targets offer a number of advantages over other types of imaging devices. With multiplexing, high frequency, noncontacting measurements of multiple points may be carried out on-line. Various types of area photodiodes have been described (9,10,11); however, the lateral-effect-photo-diode as first described in ref. (9), provides excellent linearity and good sensitivity characteristics for high frequency position measurements.

This report describes the development, calibration, and evaluation of an optoelectronic remote tracking measurement system, at the National Bureau of Standards (NBS), based on

lateral-effect-photo-diode detectors and cameras manufactured by SELCOM AB of Sweden. An evaluation of the usefulness of the system in robotics and various applications will form the next phase of the research project.

HARDWARE

Detector characteristics

The detector amplifier outputs of the SELSPOT 1 cameras were evaluated for noise characteristics. With the original gain settings in the camera electronics, signal variations of as much as ± 20 mV were observed with the major frequency component centered at about 130 kHz. Since the same amplitude of noise variation was present with the lens covered as well as with the camera observing pulsed LEDs, the noise is inherent to the detector/amplifier combination. The detector noise was sufficiently large to cause slight variations in the sampled integrator output signals.

More detailed detector characteristics were obtained using a spectrum analyzer to evaluate the detector with the camera lens closed (dark level) and with the camera observing an LED every 3 ms. Over a span of 500 kHz, it was observed that detector noise signal bandwidth was approximately 100 kHz, peaking at 110 kHz and at 165 kHz and ending at 200 kHz. With the camera viewing one LED, it was observed that with 50 μ s pulses, convolved lobes were obtained every 20 kHz with the convolution spectrum degenerating after the fifth lobe. The results show that 80 kHz can be chosen as the bandpass cutoff frequency. Retaining the primary lobe and three secondary lobes is more than sufficient to retain the shape of the LED pulse signal. The 80 kHz cutoff frequency allows for the attenuation of the detector/amplifier noise components. The background elimination scheme used in the integrator circuits does an excellent job of removing any 60 Hz component appearing on the detector input signals. The 60 Hz component approximates a dc offset or background level of different amplitudes at each sample point and therefore is removed as such.

The testing was done primarily to determine the possibility of eliminating or greatly reducing detector noise with state-of-the-art analog filter chips or by using a totally digital A/D converter and filter preprocessor section. The latter approach would eliminate the need for any analog integration/filter circuits. Data would be immediately digitized following the camera amplifier circuit and would be sent to the computer for any further processing. The results of this study may be incorporated at a later time.

Additional testing was also conducted to determine the amount of error due to temperature changes in the detector and camera housing. About two parts per thousand drift was measured for a 5° C change in detector temperature.

Hardware Development

The steps taken at NBS to develop an improved opto-electronic remote tracking system were based on the results of an evaluation of a SELSPOT 1 system for possible sources of error and noise. The following is a list of changes incorporated in the NBS system:

1. The camera amplifier gain was reduced to one fourth of the original gain in order to reduce the level of the amplified detector noise.
2. LED radiation intensity was increased by using higher power infrared LEDs and driver circuits. The higher intensity was necessary to compensate for the lower camera amplifier gain.
3. The entire SELSPOT 1 processor and control system was replaced with a more flexible 8086 microprocessor based/software driven system. LED pulse control and all integrator logic control signals originated in the 8086 microprocessor system under software control. It would have been extremely difficult to modify the SELSPOT 1 system to incorporate desired changes and to implement software control of LEDs and data processing.
4. Pulse integration was started only after all transients following the leading edge of the detected pulse had settled out (approximately 15 μ s following the leading edge of the 50 μ s LED driver pulse).
5. 12-bit A/D converters were selected in place of a 10 bit converter as used in the original SELSPOT 1 system. This was done to increase the system conversion resolution to approximately one part in 4000.
6. Separate 12-bit A/D converters were used for x, y and also the intensity voltage level. Compensation for intensity variations was performed in software on the new system. A software driven multiplexer was used to switch camera 1 and camera 2 signals to the A/D converters.

Hardware description

The hardware configuration for the NBS Remote Tracking System is represented schematically in Fig. 1. The two solid state cameras are from an early model SELSPOT 1 system manufactured by SELCOM. Each camera contains a large area (2.5 mm square) tetra-lateral photodiode with four electrodes as shown in Fig. 2. The preamplifiers are actually current-to-voltage converters with the amplifier input impedance being the load resistance. Detected LED x, y position data from the cameras is first processed in the pulse integrator boards before being interfaced to an 8086 microprocessor through analog to digital converter boards mounted on an S-100 bus. An LED pulse control circuit, which is under software control of the 8086 microprocessor, has adjustable intensity control with maximum current drive capability of 10 amperes for a duration of 50

μ s. High power infrared LEDs (Texas Instruments type TIES15) are fixed to objects whose locations are to be measured. Infrared light from the LEDs is focused onto the detector by a custom 50 mm, f/1.0 lens. A filter over the detector eliminates most ambient visible light. A photo-current is generated by radiation falling on the detector, and the current to each electrode is quite linearly dependent upon the distance of the light spot from the electrode. For extended or unfocused light sources the outputs correspond to the integrated centroid of all the radiation incident upon the detector. Hence focusing is unnecessary for most applications, and no focusing mechanism is provided on the cameras. However, for close range measurements at large lens apertures, a spacing ring of appropriate thickness was installed between the lens shoulder and camera housing to ensure that all of the radiation from the LED falls upon the detector surface. The detector photo-currents are amplified by preamplifier and amplifier stages contained in the camera housing. The four detector analog voltage signals denoted by x1, x2, y1, and y2 correspond to the converter amplified electrode currents indicated in Fig. 2. The signals are further amplified before being sent to the integration circuits.

By use of time division multiplexing, the directions of a number of LEDs can be sequentially measured and identified by each camera. The NBS system utilizes software to control all timing and signal conditioning and allows the multiplexing of up to eight LEDs.

A schematic diagram of the circuits used to integrate and condition the analog signals before A/D conversion is presented in Fig. 3. The NBS integrator boards functionally perform much like the pulse shaper boards of the original SELSPOT 1 system; however, considerable effort was made in trying to minimize all possible sources of error and noise. High quality electronic components were used wherever possible. Ultra stable, highly regulated precision power supplies were used to provide power for the integrator boards as well as the cameras. High speed opto-isolators were used to couple the integrate, reset and sample logic signals to the integrator boards in an attempt to keep the analog and digital(processor) grounds separated and to minimize noise.

The input circuits on the integrator boards consist of three operational amplifiers. The first two measure the difference between x1 and x2, and y1 and y2, while the third measures the sum of the detector signals. The signals are then processed by the integrator electronics. The process begins with the integration of the detector signal background level just prior to the LED pulse. This level is clamped or held until it can be subtracted from the pulse integrator signal level which is obtained about 50 μ s later. The differential instrumentation amplifier outputs the background eliminated signal level to a high speed, high accuracy sample and hold circuit which latches the signal in preparation for analog to digital conversion.

Finally, the outputs X, Y and intensity I for each camera feed into a multiplexer circuit which, under software control, switches either camera 1 or camera 2 signals to the A/D converters located on the processor system S-100 bus.

The A/D converters utilized are standard S-100 boards having a resolution of 12 bits. The X, Y, and I (intensity) outputs from the integrator circuits are digitized by individual A/D boards. Such an arrangement enables higher sampling rates and reduces noise that would be introduced by additional multiplexing circuits.

Hardware Calibration and Adjustment

Since the gain of the SELSPOT 1 camera amplifiers was reduced to one fourth of the original gain setting, a recalibration of the camera electronics was in order. The calibration was performed using the technique suggested in the SELSPOT 1 technical manual. The new pulse integrator boards were first tested and adjusted for amplifier offset and gain. A precision voltage source was used to provide the dc reference voltages to the integrator boards. Adjustments were made to \pm 0.001 V.

Dynamic calibration of the integrator boards was also performed. A precision pulse generator was synchronized to the LED pulse signals and was used to provide an input signal to a LED pulse simulator circuits. A calibration circuit was built to provide precisely controlled pulses to the integration circuit board of each camera. Precision multiturn potentiometers provided proportional amplitude control of the x1, x2 and y1, y2 signals. Pulse height variations, due to slope changes and noise, were kept to less than \pm 2 mV. This approach thoroughly evaluated the performance of the integrator circuits under dynamic signal conditions.

CALIBRATION PROCEDURES

Calibration of the three dimensional measurement system was implemented at three levels; the A/D converters, the individual camera system including optics, detector, and analog electronics, and the three dimensional configuration to determine the camera locations and orientations with respect to a reference coordinate system. This section describes the approach and implementation of each calibration procedure.

A/D converter calibration

A series of tests made on the A/D's demonstrated that non-linearities, although generally within specifications, did cause significant errors when multiple readings were averaged to provide a

resolution in excess of 12 bits. The errors were appreciably larger where switching occurred in the higher order bits. To minimize such errors each A/D board was calibrated by connecting it to a programmable precision voltage source which was stepped through the range 0 to 5 volts in increments of 0.2mV. The mean values of multiple measurements made by the A/D converter were then identified at the center of each bit increment and stored in a 4096 element lookup table.

Camera calibration

Evaluation of the camera systems indicated a number of sources of error. Errors were determined to come from the optics, detector irregularities, the dependence of the output coordinates X and Y upon the intensity I, and nonlinearities in the analog signal conditioning circuits. The intensity errors arise from the difficulty of precisely setting gains on all amplifiers and summing circuits as well as an apparent contribution from the detector itself, and were found to be particularly severe at low intensity levels. Without software corrections or some form of intensity control through a feedback loop (as implemented in the new version of the SELSPOT system (12)), intensity errors reached a magnitude of several percent of full scale in each dimension. In order to correct for all of these errors, a software procedure for mapping the X, Y, and I values output by the system into corrected X and Y was implemented for each camera. These corrected coordinates will be called X' and Y'. The experimental procedure involved setting up each camera in front of a flat-bed digital plotter which was used to position an LED at a series of control points. This plotter has a rated accuracy of 66 μm (0.0025 in.) and repeatability was measured to be better than 30 μm (0.0012 in.). The camera was carefully placed so that the perpendicular from the center of the control point area passed through the center of the lens. The control point area utilized was 254 mm (10 in) square, and the camera had to be placed approximately 670 mm from the plotter surface to fill its field of view. Under program control, the plotter carriage with the LED was moved to 26 x 26 grid points. At each position, 100 measurements of the LED direction were collected and averaged. To vary the intensity of the light received by the camera, the current to the LED could be manually adjusted. Normally, six intensity levels were used in each camera calibration, resulting in the collection of data on 26 x 26 x 6 points over a time period of approximately 30 minutes. From the raw calibration data, a three dimensional look-up table mapping X, Y, and I into the corrected coordinates X' and Y' was calculated as described next.

The intensity of the light from an LED as measured by a camera depends upon the following factors. The camera lens aperture, the distance of the LED from the camera, the orientation of the LED to the camera, the current through the LED, the

temperature of the LED, and the type of LED used. Variations in output from different LEDs of the same type may also be quite large. For these reasons, the LED intensity measured at a single current varied considerably over the control point area. The first step of the lookup table calculation was to linearly interpolate the X and Y coordinates to obtain coordinates corresponding to constant intensities. Because the intensity errors are nonlinear with respect to the measured intensity, a transformation to a variable analogous to LED distance ($D = k/\sqrt{I}$) which is reasonably linear with error was used. The interpolation intensity planes are then separated by equal increments of D and allows accurate linear interpolation. Two dimensional quadratic interpolation of X and Y was then carried out to obtain the true or corrected coordinates occurring at equal increments of the measured coordinates within each constant intensity plane. Whereas the initial data gave the measured coordinates at equal increments of the true coordinates at approximately constant intensities, the final lookup table gives the true coordinates at equal increments of measured coordinates, at a number of constant intensities. The lookup table size calculated was 24 x 24 x 6 for each camera, and allowed the rapid computation of corrected X and Y coordinates from the measured X, Y, and I by three dimensional linear interpolation.

Three-dimensional calibration

For 3D measurements, the image coordinates of at least two cameras must be used to reconstruct the 3D locations of the LEDs. The minimum data required to calculate the 3D position are the direction of the LED as measured by each camera in the camera coordinate system and the location and orientation of each camera with respect to a reference coordinate system. The determination of the external camera parameters (location and orientation) is not a trivial problem, but a number of techniques are available (13,14). From the experimental viewpoint, the ability to arbitrarily place the cameras in suitable locations and then calculate their parameters from a set of measurements on static control points is very desirable. Such a technique provides the flexibility to easily carry out measurements in a variety of set-ups using any number of cameras and allows for portability of the system. A method similar to the Direct Linear Transformation (13) has been implemented for the NBS system. The computer program computes the six external camera parameters of position and orientation and the principal distance (cardinal point to detector distance) from image coordinates of a minimum of four control points whose locations are specified in a reference coordinate system. A least squares fit calculation is used to find the camera parameters such that the sum of the squared distances between the rays measured by the camera and the control points is a minimum. The solution that provides the minimum least squares value is a useful indicator of the consistency of the solution. Once these parameters are known for two or more cameras, the three dimensional coordinates

of any LED may be computed from the image coordinates output by the cameras.

For the 3D calibration the cameras are placed so that their optical axes form an angle of approximately 90 degrees. Such an arrangement provides optimum accuracy in all three dimensions (15). One hundred measurements of a set of control points are collected by each camera and averaged. After the A/D and camera corrections have been applied, the camera parameters are calculated and stored in a data file. Once the 3D configuration has been determined, it remains in effect until the cameras are moved. The control points may then be removed from the measurement volume.

TESTING

Following the calibrations of the various parts of the measurement system, a series of tests were carried out to determine its accuracy, noise, sampling rate, and repeatability. Each type of test will now be described and the results presented.

Camera calibration accuracy and repeatability

While each camera was set up for the camera calibration measurements, additional data collections were performed for the purpose of checking the ability of the lookup correction tables to accurately correct for the various nonlinearities of the system. The second data set involved moving the target LED to the mid-positions of the grid cells generated by the plotter and utilized five intensity settings halfway between the six used for the calibration data. A third data set was acquired using a repeat of the calibration data set collection procedure.

After the lookup tables had been computed using the calibration measurement set, the tables were applied to all three sets of data. The differences between true positions of the target LED and the positions obtained by applying the tables to the first (calibration) data set were interpreted as being due to computation errors and the inability of the quadratic curve fitting to accommodate localized nonlinearities. The lookup tables were applied to the second set to verify the ability of the tables to adequately correct measurements over the entire area of the image. Errors due to the inadequacy of the lookup tables to correct the measurements may be expected to be largest in locations furthest from the points which were used to calculate the tables, i.e., at the mid-points of the grid cells. The tables were used with the third data set to measure the repeatability of the camera system. Table 1 lists the ranges of the mean errors, and standard deviation about the mean error, for x and y of each camera when the lookup corrections were applied to each of the three data sets.

data	CAMERA 1				CAMERA 2			
	mean error		SD of error		mean error		SD of error	
set	min.	max.	min.	max.	min.	max.	min.	max.
1:X	-3.52	-0.36	0.66	1.39	-2.81	-0.17	0.73	1.69
1:Y	-0.73	-0.35	0.73	1.73	-0.43	-0.18	1.03	2.52
2:X	-4.16	-1.88	1.15	3.25	-7.19	-3.05	1.26	2.32
2:Y	0.05	1.43	1.25	3.25	0.01	1.90	2.52	3.46
3:X	-2.63	1.68	1.06	2.69	-7.50	-0.96	0.98	3.19
3:Y	0.81	1.49	1.62	3.81	1.28	2.51	3.49	5.20

Table 1. Ranges of means of errors, and standard deviations of errors about means for the individual cameras. Units are parts per 10,000 of the field of view.

In general, the standard deviation of the error about the mean error tended to increase with decreasing intensity. Such a result was expected because at lower intensities the signal-to-noise ratio is smaller. Also, it was postulated that the major source of the errors presented in Table 1 were due to temperature changes of the detector and the camera housing during the test. Detector temperature drift was reported in the section on hardware. Hence, attempts to improve upon the present accuracy must include control of camera temperature or some method of correcting for the temperature related errors.

Resolution

The resolution of the system depends upon the resolution of A/D converters and the amount of noise present in the signal being digitized. A system exhibiting zero noise would have the same resolution as the A/D converters measuring the signal, i.e. 1 part in 4096 in the present case. By averaging the output in static measurements, or filtering as in the case of dynamic measurements, a certain level of white noise can provide for a higher resolution than the resolution inherent in the A/D converters alone. For the system under investigation, a resolution of 1 part per 10,000 along each dimension was easily attained when 100 readings were averaged for each position measurement.

Tests were performed to measure the effects of noise in the measurements carried out by the individual camera systems. The tests were carried out at 80% of the maximum intensity that could be accommodated. For a set of locations covering the field of view, the system was programmed to measure the position of a stationary LED by the use of a number of readings ranging from 1 to 1000. The standard deviation about the mean for 100 measurements, each measurement taking the required number of readings, ranged from 1.30 for 1 reading to 0.48 parts per 10,000 for 1000 readings for the x-coordinate, when the LED was in the center of the field of view. These values

were approximately doubled at the edges of the field of view. The y-coordinates showed similar values.

Measurement rate

The original Selspot system was able to time multiplex thirty LEDs at a sampling rate of approximately 330 Hz/LED for two cameras. The maximum sampling rate of the system could have possibly been increased to 10 kHz/LED if all 30 of the LED driver lines were tied to a single LED. In contrast to the Selspot system which controlled the measurements in hardware, the NBS system is controlled by software running on an 8086 microprocessor. This feature allows for complete control over pulse time and integration times among others. The fundamental sampling rate was approximately 5.1 kHz/LED if one camera is used, and 3.3 kHz/LED if both cameras are used. The present version of the 3D transformation software allows the output of 3D LED coordinates at a rate of 40 Hz. However, with some optimization of the software, real time measurement rates of 200 Hz using the 8086 processor are anticipated.

Accuracy in three dimensions

The three dimensional accuracy of the complete system was tested using a coordinate measurement system having a measurement accuracy of at least 1 to 2 orders of magnitude better along each axis of motion. The two cameras were mounted 1.50 m apart on a beam which was parallel to the x-axis and fixed to the table which moves along the z-axis. The target LED was attached to the probe arm which could be positioned in the x-y plane. A number of cubic grids were generated under program control, and at each grid point a measurement using 100 readings was recorded for both cameras. Various sets of the grid points were used for the 3D calibration of the system, with the rest utilized to compute the errors of the 3D measurements. Table 2 and 3 summarize the results for measurements carried out on two cubic grids. All measurements are in mm.

Grid	No. of Points	Size	Camera dist.		Angle (deg)	%field used	
			C1	C2		C1	C2
1	5x5x5	160.0	1100.	1251.	87	52	50
2	6x6x6	300.0	1242.	1327.	73	95	90

Table 2. Measurement conditions for two cubic grids used to test the 3D accuracy of the system. The angles are those between the optical axes of the cameras.

One 3D calibrations was performed using half of the points in the grids: another using only eight points in each grid. When half of the points were used, the points chosen were uniformly distributed throughout the grid. When eight points were used, the points selected were located at the corners of

the middle size cube for Grid 2 and the smaller cube of Grid 1. Ideally, a large number of control points should be used for the 3D calibration. However, since in many situations it is not practical to use a large number of control points, it was of interest to see if the use of a smaller number of points degraded the accuracy of the calibration.

Grid	No. of points used for calib.	Mean error of remaining pts.			SD of errors about mean		
		X	Y	Z	X	Y	Z
1	8	.008	.004	-.015	.097	.059	.084
1	62	-.007	-.004	-.004	.084	.059	.058
2	8	.021	.000	.010	.337	.264	.251
2	108	.004	.085	.004	.414	.270	.309

Table 3. Errors and standard deviations about the means for three dimensional measurements after 3D calibration using the specified number of points.

From the results summarized in Table 3, and additional measurements, the total system accuracy in 3D was determined to be approximately 1 part in 2000 when data points were taken within the center 80 percent of the detector field of view. System accuracy degraded to 1 part in 1000 when data points outside the center 90 percent of the field of view were included for 3D calibration of the system. The mean errors were very small because the 3D calibration procedure computed the camera parameters by minimizing the RMS distances between calibration points and the measured ray directions. The standard deviations about the means are good indicators of the errors that can be expected in application of the system. The errors increased as the percentage of the field used increased for several reasons. The detectors are less linear and the signal-to-noise ratios for some of the outputs are smaller near the electrodes. Additionally, a non-focused LED image may not fall entirely on the detector, and the lookup tables cannot be computed as accurately near the edges of the field-of-view. The results also indicate that the use of just eight control points gave results of essentially the same accuracy as the use of 62 and 108 points.

The extension of measurements to larger volumes is not expected to pose any difficulties. Ideally, the lookup correction tables should be calculated by moving the LED over an area located at the mean distance of the measurement volume. Using this procedure, any changes in the LED images and LED pulse characteristics due to higher currents necessary for operations at the larger distances would be included in the lookup corrections.

CONCLUSIONS

An optoelectronic system capable of high speed, on-line, three-dimensional measurements, with a degree of accuracy in dynamic applications superior to any other system, has been described.

Such systems are already being implemented for robot evaluation and performance testing (12). This study has addressed some of the problems of attaining maximum accuracy and evaluated many aspects of a system based on large area photodiode detectors. An absolute accuracy of approximately 1 part in 2000, in 3D, was achieved by careful calibration of the system components and by using data points within the center 80 percent of the detector field of view for 3D calibration of the total system. It appears that an absolute accuracy of 1 part in 10,000 along each dimension of a working volume might be attained with suitable calibration techniques and the use of higher resolution A/D converters. However, the attainment of such accuracy in a practical environment is unlikely. Even in a very controlled laboratory environment, the errors caused by reflections of the infrared light from surfaces and objects within the field of view of a camera, result in errors considerably exceeding this limit.

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NOTE

Certain commercial equipment, instruments or materials are identified in this paper in order to adequately specify the experimental procedure. Such identification does not imply recommendation or endorsement by the National Bureau of Standards nor does it imply that the materials or equipment identified are necessarily the best available for the purpose.

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* STANDARD 12 BIT A/D CONVERTER BOARDS FOR S-100

** SELSPOT 1 CAMERAS

FIG. 1
NBS OPTOELECTRONIC REMOTE TRACKING SYSTEM

FIG. 2
TETRA-LATERAL PHOTODIODE WITH PREAMPLIFIERS

FIG. 3
INTEGRATOR/MUX. CIRCUIT BOARDS